

A SURVEY ON RELATIVE PARACOMPACTNESS

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Abstract

In this paper we survey the various kinds of relative paracompactness. We first consider the Aull's concept of α -paracompact subsets, its properties and applications, then review other notions of relative paracompactness and end by proposing some open problems.

Keywords: α -paracompact subset, well situated subset, relative paracompactness, β -paracompact subset, σ -paracompact subset.

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0. Introduction

In this paper we give a survey on the various kinds of relative paracompactness studied by many mathematicians since 1966,

when the first definition of paracompactness for subsets was proposed by C.E. Aull: the α -paracompact subsets.

C.E. Aull's paper was followed by others, whose authors either considered different questions concerning such sets or proposed alternative definitions of relative paracompactness and developed their own results.

The number of existing publications, and the diversity of directions and applications fully justify the preparation of this survey.

1. The notion of α -paracompact subset. Properties

The α -paracompactness is the main concept of relative paracompactness.

Definition 1.1

[Au1] A subset M of a topological space (X, T) is α -paracompact in X if every cover of M by open subsets of (X, T) has a refinement by open, locally finite in X , which covers M .

Aull obtained some results on α -paracompact subsets analogous to those valid for compact sets:

Theorem 1.1

[Au1] Let (X, T) be T_2 , M be α -paracompact in X , and $x \notin M$. Then x and M are strongly separated.

Theorem 1.2

[Au1] Let (X, T) be T_2 and let M and N be disjoint α -paracompact subsets in X . Then M and N are strongly separated.

Theorem 1.3

[Au1] Let (X, T) be regular and let M be α -paracompact in X and F closed in X , $M \cap F = \phi$. Then M is strongly separated from F .

Theorem 1.4

[Au1] In a regular space the closure of an α -paracompact subset is α -paracompact.

P. Kessler [Ke] rediscovered the notion which he called strictly paracompactness, and obtained results analogous to Aull's.

The same concept has been introduced also by R. A. Alò and H. L. Shapiro [Al-Sh] who called the sets strongly paracompact and obtained the following results.

Theorem 1.5

[Al-Sh] If X is a normal T_2 topological space and S is a subset of X , then the following statement are equivalent:

- (1) S is strongly paracompact.
- (2) S is paracompact and P -embedded in X .

(A subspace S is P -embedded in X if every continuous pseudometric on S extends to a continuous pseudometric on X).

Theorem 1.6

[Al-Sh] If S is a closed subset of a collectionwise normal space X , then S is paracompact if and only if S is strongly paracompact.

Theorem 1.7

[Al-Sh] If F is a strongly paracompact subset of the closed subspace S of (X, T) and if there is an open set G in X such that $F \subset G \subset S$, then F is strongly paracompact in X .

Kessler, and Alò and Shapiro considered also slight modifications of the concept of α -paracompactness: strictly m -paracompactness and strongly m -paracompactness, where m is an infinite cardinal number, and obtained analogous results to those related to α -paracompact sets.

In 1977, C. M. Pareek and H. Z. Hdeib recalled relatively paracompact to the α -paracompact subsets. The main results of their paper are:

Theorem 1.8

[P-H] Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a continuous and closed mapping of X onto Y . Then f is a m -paraperfect mapping if $f^{-1}(y)$ is relatively m -paracompact for each y in Y (A continuous mapping $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is called m -paraperfect if for every open cover $\mathcal{U}$ of X with cardinality $\leq m$, there is an open cover $\mathcal{V}$ of Y and an open refinement $\mathcal{W}$ of $\mathcal{U}$ such that for each $V \in \mathcal{V}$, $f^{-1}(V)$ is contained in the union of a locally finite subfamily of $\mathcal{W}$).

Theorem 1.9

[P-H] Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a continuous function where X is a regular space. Let $\{C_s\}_{s \in S}$ and $\{U_s\}_{s \in S}$ be two coverings of Y satisfying

- (a) $\{C_s\}_{s \in S}$ is a closed covering of Y and $\{U_s\}_{s \in S}$ is an open ordered locally finite covering of Y such that $C_s \subset U_s$ for each $s \in S$.
- (b) $f^{-1}(C_s)$ is relatively paracompact, for each $s \in S$.

Then X is paracompact.

In 1975, J. D. Wine applied Aull's concept of α -paracompactness to paracompatifications (we will see this in Section 2).

Theorem 1.10

[W2] Let E be an α -paracompact subset of a locally paracompact regular space, and G be any open set containing E . Then there is a closed α -paracompact neighborhood of E contained in G .

In 1984, I. Kovačević studied also some related concepts:

Definition 1.2

[Ko 5] A subset E of a space X is a α -regular if for any point $x \in E$ and any open set U of X containing x , there exists an open set V of X such that $x \in V \subset \bar{V} \subset U$.

Theorem 1.11

[Ko 5] If E is an α -regular α -paracompact subset of a space X , U an open neighbourhood of E , then there exists an open neighbourhood V of E such that $E \subset V \subset \bar{V} \subset U$.

In 1985, F. G. Lupiáñez established various properties of α -paracompact subsets:

Theorem 1.12

[L 1,2,3] Let X be a topological space. Then:

- 1) If E is an α -paracompact subset in X and F is a subset on E which is closed in X , then F is α -paracompact in X .
- 2) If $\{E_j\}_{j \in J}$ is a family of subsets of X , locally finite in X and such that each E_j is α -paracompact in X and there exists a locally finite family of open subsets $\{U_j\}_{j \in J}$ of X such that $E_j \subset U_j$ for every $j \in J$, then $\bigcup_{j \in J} E_j$ is α -paracompact in X .

We also characterized α -paracompact subsets in regular spaces:

Theorem 1.13

[L 1,2,3] Let X be a regular space and E be a subset of X . The following conditions are equivalent:

- a) E is an α -paracompact subset in X .
- b) 1) Every covering $\mathcal{U}$ of E by open subsets of X has a refinement $\mathcal{V}$ by open subsets of X , σ -locally finite in X , which covers E , and 2) Every open subset U of X such that $E \subset U$ has an open subset V that $E \subset V \subset \bar{V} \subset U$.
- c) Every covering $\mathcal{U}$ of E by open subsets of X has a refinement $\mathcal{A} = \{A_s\}_{s \in S}$ by arbitrary sets of X , locally finite in X , such that $E \subset \text{int} \bigcup_{s \in S} A_s$.
- d) Every covering $\mathcal{U}$ of E by open subsets of X has a refinement $\mathcal{F} = \{F_j\}_{j \in J}$ by closed subsets of X , locally finite in X , such that $E \subset \text{int} \bigcup_{s \in S} A_s$.

Theorem 1.14

[L 1,2,3] Let X be a regular space and E an α -paracompact subset in X . Then:

- 1) Every covering $\mathcal{U}$ of E by open subsets of X has a refinement by open subsets of X , barycentric in X , which covers E .
- 2) Every covering $\mathcal{U}$ of E by open subsets of X has a star refinement by open subsets of X which covers E .

Theorem 1.15

[L 1,2,3] Let X be a regular space and E an α -paracompact subset in E . Then for every family $\{F_s\}_{s \in S}$ of subsets of E , locally finite (discrete) in X , there is a family $\{U_s\}_{s \in S}$ of open subsets of X , locally finite (discrete) in X , such that $F_s \subset U_s$ for every $s \in S$.

Moreover we studies that behaviour of α -paracompact subsets under perfect mappings:

Theorem 1.16

[L 1, 2, 3] Let X and X' be topological spaces and $f : X \rightarrow X'$ a perfect mapping. If E' is an α -paracompact subset in X' then $f^{-1}(E')$ is an α -paracompact subset in X .

Theorem 1.17

[L 1, 2, 3] Let X and X' be topological spaces, where X is regular, f a perfect mapping from X onto X' and E' a subset of X' . If $f^{-1}(E')$ is an α -paracompact subset in X , then E' is an α -paracompact subset in X' .

Theorem 1.18

[L 1, 2, 3] Let X and X' be topological spaces and f a perfect and open mapping from X onto X' . If E is an α -paracompact subset in X then $f(E)$ is an α -paracompact subset in X' .

In 1988, H. Z. Hdeib proved the following:

Theorem 1.19

[H] Let E be a closed subset of a space X . Then the following are equivalent: (a) E is α -paracompact; b) E is paracompact and the boundary is α -paracompact.

Theorem 1.20

[H] Let X be a T_1 space. Then the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is paracompact.
- (b) Every closed subset of X is α -paracompact.
- (c) The set of non-isolated points of X is α -paracompact.

Many other results on α -paracompact subsets were obtained by I. Kovačević:

Theorem 1.21

[Ko 6] Let E be a dense α -regular subset of a space X such that every open covering of E is an open covering of X . If X is almost paracompact, then E is α -paracompact.

Theorem 1.22

[Ko 6] Let f be a closed and continuous mapping of a space X onto a space Y , let B be any α -paracompact subset of Y such that for each $y \in B$, $f^{-1}(y)$ is α -paracompact, then $f^{-1}(B)$ is α -paracompact.

Theorem 1.23

[Ko 7] In any space the union of a locally finite family of open α -paracompact, α -regular sets, is a closed, α -regular, α -paracompact set.

Theorem 1.24

[Ko 8] Let D be any dense α -regular subset of a space X such that every open covering of D is open covering of X . Then X is paracompact if and only if D is a α -paracompact.

Theorem 1.25

[Ko 8] Let D be a dense α -regular subset of a space X . Then, D is α -paracompact if and only if every open covering of D has a closure preserving open refinement.

Theorem 1.26

[Ko 8] Let D be a dense T_1 α -paracompact subset of a normal space X . If f is a closed and continuous mapping of the space X onto a space Y , then Y is paracompact.

Definition 1.3

[Ko 5] A subset E of a space X is α -Hausdorff if any two points a and b such that $a \in E$ and $b \in X \setminus E$, can be strongly separated.

Theorem 1.27

[Ko 9] Let X be any topological space such that every closed subset is α -Hausdorff. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a closed mapping of a space X onto a compact space Y such that for each point $y \in Y$, $f^{-1}(y)$ is an α -Hausdorff α -paracompact subset of a space X . Then X is regular.

Definition 1.4

[Ko 12] A space X is D_p if it has an α -paracompact dense subset.

Theorem 1.28

[Ko 12] Every D_p space is almost paracompact.

2. Applications of α -paracompactness

The concept of α -paracompact subset has been applied to

some questions.

In 1973, J. D. Wine introduced the notion of filter base, studied their convergence and other properties.

Definition 2.1

[W 1] An α -filter base is a family $\mathcal{F}$ of non empty zero sets satisfying:

- (1) If Z is in $\mathcal{F}$ then Z is not α -paracompact, and
- (2) If U and V are in $\mathcal{F}$ then their intersection contains an element of $\mathcal{F}$.

Theorem 2.1

[W 1] If $\mathcal{B}$ is an α -filter base, then there is a maximal α -filter base which contains $\mathcal{B}$.

Theorem 2.2

[W 1] Let X be a completely regular space. Then X is paracompact if and only if there is no free α -filter base on X . Also X is paracompact if and only if there is no free maximal α -filter base.

Wine also proposed the construction of paracompactifications based on the addition of limit points to the α -filter bases.

Definition 2.2

[W 1] Let K be an index set for the maximal α -filter bases on X , then define $\mathcal{A}_F(X)$ to be $\{\mathcal{F}_k | k \in K \text{ and } \mathcal{F}_k \text{ is a free maximal } \alpha\text{-filter base}\}$ For each set G in X define $K(G)$ to be $\{k | k \in K \text{ and there is a } F \text{ in } \mathcal{F}_k \text{ contained in } G\}$.

Theorem 2.3

[W 1] Let $\pi X = \{y_k | k \in K, y_k \text{ is not in } X\} \cup X$ and $\mathcal{B} = \{H | H = G \cup \{y_k | k \in K(G)\} \text{ where } G \text{ is a cozero set}\}$. Then $\mathcal{B}$ is a base for a topology on πX .

Theorem 2.4

[W 1] πX is paracompact.

Theorem 2.5

[W 1] A completely regular Hausdorff space X is locally paracompact if and only if X is open in πX .

Other application of α -paracompactness is the concept of well-situated subset.

Definition 2.3

[Te] A subset E of a space X is said to be well-situated in X if for every paracompact T_2 space Y , $E \times Y$ is an α -paracompact subset in $X \times Y$.

This concept has been introduced by R. Telgársky in the context of a problem of H. Tamano [Ta], namely to give an intrinsic characterization of the T_2 spaces X such that $X \times Y$ is paracompact for each paracompact T_2 space Y . This problem, proposed in 1962, remains open. Some of the properties of well-situated subsets were established in [L 1, 2, 3].

R. Telgársky denoted by Π^* the class of all paracompact T_2 spaces which are well-situated in every paracompact T_2 space in which they are embedded as closed subsets. He showed that Π^* is a very wide subclass of Π , the class of all T_2 spaces X such that $X \times Y$ is paracompact for each paracompact T_2 space Y , and he raised the following problem: Is the class Π^* perfect? [Te].

We have given an affirmative answer to this question.

Theorem 2.6

[L 2,3] Let E, E' be topological spaces where E is T_2 , and f is a perfect mapping from E onto E' . If $E' \in \Pi^*$ then $E \in \Pi^*$.

Theorem 2.7

[L 2,3] Let E and E' be topological spaces and f a perfect mapping from E onto E' . If $E \in \Pi^*$ then $E' \in \Pi^*$.

Theorem 2.8

[L 2,3] In the realm of T_2 spaces, the class Π^* is perfect.

Using the concept of α -paracompactness, the various axioms of separation and embedding, we defined some classes of topological spaces: the classes $\Gamma^*(T_i)$ where $i = 2, 3, 3a, 4, 5, 5a$ and $\Gamma^*(T_j^*)$ where $j = 4, 5, 5a$. Such classes allowed us to characterize compact, Lindelöf and paracompact spaces in the realm of T_2 spaces. In fact:

Theorem 2.9

[L 1,4] A T_{3a} space is compact if and only if it is α -paracompact in each T_{3a} space in which it is embedded as a closed subset.

Theorem 2.10

[L 1,4] A T_4 space is Lindelöf if and only if it is α -paracompact in each T_4 space in which it is embedded as a closed subset.

Theorem 2.11

[L 1,4] A collectionwise normal T_1 space is paracompact if and only if it is α -paracompact in each collectionwise normal T_1 space in which is embedded as a closed subset.

In 1989, we introduced some covering properties related to paracompactness, which allowed us to characterize paracompact, compact, pseudocompact, lightly compact, collectionwise

normal with respect to paracompact and closed sets, and countably compact spaces. For example:

Theorem 2.12

[L-O] Let X be a T_2 space, then X is lightly paracompact if and only if every α -paracompact subset of X is compact.

Theorem 2.13

[L-O] Let X be a $T_{3\alpha}$ space, then X is pseudocompact if and only if all α -paracompact subset of X is compact.

In 1999, we introduced some types of fuzzy paracompactness for fuzzy subsets. For that, we adopted Luo's definition of fuzzy paracompactness.

Definition 2.4

[L 5] Let (X, T) be a fuzzy topological space, μ a fuzzy set in (X, T) and $r \in (0, 1]$. We will say that μ is r -paracompact (resp. r^* -paracompact) relative to (X, T) if for each $r-Q$ -cover of μ by open sets in (X, T) , there exists an open refinement of it which is both locally finite (resp. $*$ -locally finite) in (X, T) and $r-Q$ -cover of μ . μ will be called S -paracompact (resp. S^* -paracompact) relative to (X, T) if for every $r \in (0, 1]$, μ is r -paracompact (resp. r^* -paracompact) relative to (X, T) .

We gave the relationship between α -paracompactness, and the different fuzzy relative paracompactness, and some properties of these new fuzzy subsets:

Theorem 2.14

[L 5] Let (X, T) be a weakly induced fuzzy topological space, and $Y \subset X$. The following conditions are equivalent:

- 1) χ_Y is S^* -paracompact relative to (X, T) .
- 2) There exists a $r \in (0, 1)$ such that χ_Y is r^* -paracompact

relative to (X, T) .

3) χ_Y is S -paracompact relative to (X, T) .

4) There exists a $r \in (0, 1)$ such that χ_Y is r -paracompact relative to (X, T) .

5) Y is α -paracompact in $(X, [T])$.

Theorem 2.15

[L 5] Let (X, T) be a weakly induced fuzzy topological space, μ a fuzzy set in (X, T) , and $r \in (0, 1)$. The following conditions are equivalent:

a) μ is r^* -paracompact relative to (X, T) .

b) μ is r -paracompact relative to (X, T) .

c) $\text{supp } \mu_{\langle r \rangle}$ is α -paracompact in $(X, [T])$.

Theorem 2.16

[L 6] Let (X, T) and (Y, S) be two T_2 weakly induced fuzzy topological spaces and $f : (X, [T]) \rightarrow (Y, [S])$ an onto map. We denote $\tilde{f} : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ the map defined by $\tilde{f}(x_\alpha)(y) = \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(y)} \{x_\alpha(t)\}$ for each fuzzy point x_α in X . Let $\tilde{f}$ be fuzzy perfect in the sense of Christoph (resp. Srivastara and Lal, or Ghosh), μ be a fuzzy set in (Y, S) and $r \in (0, 1)$.

1) If μ is r -paracompact (resp. r^* -paracompact) relative to (Y, S) , then $\tilde{f}^{-1}(\mu)$ is r -paracompact (resp. r^* -paracompact) relative to (X, T) .

2) If (X, T) is regular and $\tilde{f}^{-1}(\mu)$ is r -paracompact (resp. r^* -paracompact) relative to (X, T) , then μ is r -paracompact (resp. r^* -paracompact) relative to (Y, S) .

3. Other relative versions of paracompactness.

We start with various generalizations of Aull's α -paracompact subsets.

I. Kovačević introduced and investigated the following:

Definition 3.1

[Ko 1] Let X be a topological space, and E be a subset of X . The set E is α -nearly paracompact if every regular open cover in X of E , has an open in X refinement which covers E and is locally finite in X .

Definition 3.2

[Ko 1] Let X be a topological space and E be a subset of X . The set E is α -nearly strongly paracompact if every regular open cover in X of E , has an open in X star finite refinement which covers E .

Definition 3.3

[Ko 1] Let X be a topological space and E be a subset of X . The set E is α -almost paracompact if for every open cover in X of E there exists a locally finite in X family of open sets in X , which refines it and the X -closures of whose members cover E .

He proved, for these subsets, properties of α -paracompactness type.

Ergun and Noiri defined and investigated other generalizations:

Definition 3.4

[E-N 1] A subset E of a space X is said to be α^* -paracompact if for each cover $\mathcal{U}$ of E by open sets in X , there exists a locally finite in X family $\mathcal{V}$ of open sets of X , which refines $\mathcal{U}$ and a

nowhere dense subset N_E of X such that $E \subset \bigcup_{V \in \mathcal{V}} V \cup N_E$.

Definition 3.5

[E-N 2] A subset E of a space X is said to be α -paracompact modulo an ideal $\mathcal{J}$ if for any open in X , cover of E , $\mathcal{U}$, there exists $I \in \mathcal{J}$ and a locally finite in X family $\mathcal{V}$ of open sets of X such that $\mathcal{V}$ refines $\mathcal{U}$ and $E \subset \bigcup_{V \in \mathcal{V}} V \cup I$.

Much before these studies, C. E. Aull (1967) had already distinguished other types of paracompact subsets:

Definition 3.6

[Au 1] A subset E of a topological space X is σ -paracompact if every cover of E by open sets in X has an open σ -locally finite in X refinement which covers E .

Definition 3.7

[Au 1] A subset E of a topological space X is β -paracompact if E is paracompact subspace of X . In [Au 1,2,3], some relations between the two definitions and α -paracompactness are established.

In 1984, J. P. Schneiders introduced the notion which he called "relative pracomactness":

Definition 3.8

[Sc] A subset E of a topological space X is relatively paracompact in X if every cover of E by open sets in X has an open refinement which covers E and is locally finite in E .

He proved some simples results and applied them to Sheaf Theory.

Back in 1948, J. Abdelhay had established the following:

Theorem 3.1

[Ab] The following conditions on a T_2 space are equivalent:
1) given an open covering $\mathcal{U}$ of X and a point $a \in X$, there exists an open refinement $\mathcal{V}$ of $\mathcal{U}$ such that $\mathcal{V}$ is locally finite at a , and 2) X is regular.

This result has been rediscovered by J. Chew in 1972 and J. M. Boyte in 1973.

Theorem 3.2

[Ab] A T_2 space X is normal if and only if, each open covering $\mathcal{U}$ of X has, for each $U \in \mathcal{U}$ and each closed set $F \subset U$ an open refinement which is locally finite in F .

In 1973, J. M. Boyte proved the following:

Theorem 3.3

[B] If X is T_2 , then X is normal, if and only if, each open covering $\mathcal{U}$ of X has for each $U \in \mathcal{U}$ and each closed set $F \subset U$ an open refinement which is locally finite with respect to F (i.e. there exists an open set containing the set F such that meets only finitely many members of the refinement).

The concept of paracompactness in E is defined in [Ab]. Using the hypothesis of above theorems, Lupiáñez and Outerelo introduced some new covering properties: A -paracompact in E , A -paracompact with respect to E , and paracompact with respect to E :

Definition 3.9

[L-O] Let X be a topological space and E a subset of X .

- 1) We will say that X is A -paracompact in E if every open covering $\mathcal{U}$ of X has an open refinement $\mathcal{V}$ which is locally finite in E (i.e.: in every point of E).
- 2) We will say that X is paracompact in E if every open

covering $\mathcal{U}$ of X such that $E \subset U$ for some $U \in \mathcal{U}$ has an open refinement $\mathcal{V}$ which is locally finite in E [Ab].

- 3) We will say that X is A -paracompact with respect to E if every open covering $\mathcal{U}$ of X has an open refinement $\mathcal{V}$ which is locally finite with respect to E .
- 4) We will say that X is paracompact with respect to E if every open covering $\mathcal{U}$ of X such that $E \subset U$ for some $U \in \mathcal{U}$ has an open refinement $\mathcal{V}$ which is locally finite with respect to E .

In our paper we characterized all these properties for an arbitrary closed subset, and investigated them for some other subsets. In particular we gave characterizations of lightly compact spaces and countably compact spaces using these methods (See Theorems 2.12 and 2.13).

On other hand, in 1991, I. Yu. Gordienko considered some relative topological properties like paracompactness:

Definition 3.10

[Go] Let X be a topological space and let E be a subset of X . We say that E is 1-(3-) paracompact in X , if into any open covering of X we can inscribe a covering of X (of E) by open sets in X (in E) which is locally finite in E . We say that E is 2-paracompact in X if into any open covering of X we can inscribe a family of open sets in X , which covers E and is locally finite in E (The 1-paracompactness is the "paracompact in" of J. Abdelhay). The following result extends the classical Tamano theorem to the case of 3-paracompactness.

Theorem 3.4

[Go] Let X be a $T_{3\alpha}$ space, $E \subset X$, and suppose that there exists a compactification cX of X , such that $X \times cX$ is weakly real normal in $X \times cX$. Then E is 3-paracompact in X .

(E is weakly real normal (real normal), in X if for any two disjoint sets A and B , closed in X , there exists a continuous function $f : E \rightarrow [0, 1]$ ($f : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$) such that $f(A \cap E) \subset \{0\}$ and $f(B \cap E) \subset \{1\}$).

(E is weakly normal (normal) in X if for any two disjoint sets A and B , closed in X , there exist disjoint sets U and V open in E (in X) such that $A \cap E \subset U$ and $B \cap E \subset V$).

Theorem 3.5

[Go] Let X be regular and E be 3-paracompact (2-paracompact) in X . Then for any compact T_2 space C the product space $E \times C$ is weakly normal (normal) in $X \times C$.

Finally, E. V. Gavrusenko studied paracompactness relatively to dense subsets of X :

Definition 3.11

[Ga] A space X is called d -paracompact if every open cover of X has a refinement which is locally finite in some dense subset of X .

She remarked that every metacompact Baire space is d -paracompact and gave an example of a $T_{3\alpha}$ d -paracompact space which is not metacompact.

4. Some open problems

- 1) Is α -paracompactness inverse-invariant for continuous and closed mappings?

- 2) To determine a realm of topological spaces in which the α -paracompact subsets and the well-situated subsets coincide.
- 3) Is the class Π^* productive?
- 4) Let X be a topological space, $E \subset X$. We say that E is π -embedded in X if for every T_{3a} topological space Y is $E \times Y$ P -embedded in $X \times Y$ (A. Wasko). Establish relationships between π -embedded and well-situated subsets. For example, is it possible for well-situated subsets a characterization using π -embedded subsets?

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